

From Semiotics to Multilingualism: A Critical Review of Modelling Between Digital and Humanities and Its Potentials for Extending Knowledge Infrastructures

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Abstract

This essay offers a comprehensive critical review of *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice* (Ciula, Eide, Marras, & Sahle, 2023). The book seeks to reposition modelling in Digital Humanities (DH) away from a narrowly technical conception and toward a humanistic practice of meaning-making grounded in pragmatics, metaphor, semiotics, and media transformation. Its most significant contribution lies in integrating Peircean semiotics and advocating pluralist, non-hierarchical approaches to modelling, exemplified by the “Text Wheel.” Yet the book suffers from uneven structure, redundancies, and an emphasis on description over generative methodology. It frames knowledge largely in consequentialist terms, as emerging from modelling—without developing modelling as a co-creative practice of knowledge production. Translation appears primarily as metaphorical transformation rather than a co-equal epistemic act, and multilingualism is left largely unaddressed, despite being a natural extension of the framework. A fleeting reference to a middle-out approach hints at infrastructural possibilities, but the concept is not developed. This review reconstructs the book’s conceptual framework, evaluates its strengths and limitations, and situates it in relation to broader debates in DH and the philosophy of modelling. It concludes that while the book does not deliver a fully generative framework, it provides indispensable conceptual resources for rethinking modelling as a semiotic, pluralist, and human-centered practice, and it highlights directions—translation, multilingualism, and semi-structuralism—that could extend its vision and support future developments such as a language-agnostic knowledge system.

Keywords: Digital Humanities; Pragmatic Modelling; Metaphor; Media Transformation; Language-Agnostic Knowledge (LAK); Cristina Marras; Peirce; Leibniz.

Introduction

Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice by Arianna Ciula, Øyvind Eide, Cristina Marras, and Patrick Sahle (Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2023) is both a culmination and continuation of debates that have animated Digital Humanities for two decades. Rooted in the VolkswagenStiftung-funded project *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice* (2016–2018), the book seeks to offer a “renewed language” of modelling in DH, one that foregrounds interpretation, creativity, and humanistic reasoning over purely technical formalization (Ciula et al. 2023, 1).

The central claim is that modelling in DH should not be understood merely as a computational translation of cultural data into manipulable forms. Instead, it is a *creative and pragmatic process of reasoning* in which meaning is constructed and negotiated through external representations—such as texts, diagrams, databases, visualizations, and media artifacts—that themselves constitute knowledge objects (2023, 3, 4). In this sense, the book echoes Willard McCarty’s call for modelling as the “central and distinguishing activity of the digital humanities” (McCarty 2005, 20–72), but seeks to expand it with a deeper theoretical grounding from pragmatics, metaphor theory, semiotics, and intermedia studies.

The book is organized into five chapters, each corresponding to a conceptual pillar:

1. **Pragmatic Modelling** – situating modelling as thinking-in-practice, shaped by context, intentionality, and interpretation.
2. **Metaphorical Reasoning** – presenting metaphors as models of knowledge and engines of cognition.
3. **Semiotics of Modelling** – applying Peircean semiotics to classify models as icons (image-like, diagrammatic, metaphor-like).
4. **Media Transformations** – understanding models as media products constituted by material, sensorial, spatiotemporal, and semiotic modalities.
5. **Modelling Text** – presenting an anthology of text models in an experimental “gallery” format.

The ambition is admirable: to bridge the epistemological divide between the humanities and the digital by articulating modelling as a hybrid practice that integrates formalization with interpretation, technical design with cultural analysis. Yet the book is not without flaws. Its oscillation between systematic theorization and anthology-style presentation produces unevenness, and redundancy in definitional elaborations sometimes obscures rather than clarifies. More significantly, the framework remains largely descriptive rather than generative. It acknowledges that knowledge emerges from modelling but frames this in consequentialist terms rather than treating modelling itself as a co-creative practice of knowledge production. Translation is primarily addressed as a metaphorical transformation, while its potential as a co-equal epistemic act and its implications for multilingual knowledge remain largely unexplored. Similarly, the book gestures once toward a middle-out approach but does not develop this as a structural principle for modelling or infrastructure design.

This review proceeds in four steps. Section I reconstructs the conceptual framework of the book, providing close readings of its four pillars and the final case study. Section II presents a critical analysis, highlighting both strengths and limitations, with a particular focus on the tension between description and generativity. Section III turns to the possibility of developing a language-agnostic

knowledge system, suggesting that the book provides crucial epistemological tools—especially through its focus on iconicity and pre-linguistic meaning-making, while also leaving key issues of translation, multilingualism, and semi-structuralism underdeveloped. Section IV analyses the “Text Wheel” as a case study in pluralist modelling, comparing it with Leibniz’s metaphor of the “ocean of knowledge.” The conclusion situates the book’s contribution within broader debates, acknowledging its limitations while affirming both its value and the directions in which its framework could be extended.

1. Conceptual Framework of the Book

1.1 Pragmatic Modelling: Thinking in Practice

The first chapter of *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice* sets the stage by re-framing modelling not as a rigidly formal procedure but as a pragmatic act of “thinking in practice” (Ciula et al. 2023, 3). The authors situate their approach against traditions of formalization in computer science, where modelling is often conceived as the translation of phenomena into computationally manipulable structures. Instead, they argue that modelling in Digital Humanities (DH) is a dynamic, context-sensitive process shaped by three interdependent factors: context, intentionality, and interpretation (Ciula et al. 2023, 19–23).

Context is foregrounded as a condition of modelling. Models do not emerge in isolation; they are situated events where the object of study, the modeller, and the scholarly purpose intersect. Intentionality refers to the purposive nature of modelling, where the modeller selectively emphasizes certain features of the object while ignoring others, based on goals and constraints. Interpretation marks modelling as an act of translation (Ciula et al. 2023, 12, 58, 121), where meaning is created through external representation rather than extracted from it (Ciula et al. 2023, 33–43).

The pragmatic framing situates modelling firmly within language use, echoing Verschueren’s (2012) emphasis on negotiability and adaptability in pragmatics. Models are thus not static objects but negotiable constructs subject to revision, debate, and reinterpretation. This position challenges reductive definitions of models as closed systems and instead aligns DH with traditions of abductive and analogical reasoning (Hesse 1966).

The strength of this contribution lies in its recognition that DH modelling is neither purely computational nor purely interpretive but exists at the intersection of both. Yet the discussion sometimes lapses into repetition. Multiple sections revisit the claim that models are context-bound and negotiable, without providing further methodological tools for systematically applying this principle in DH practice. As such, pragmatic modelling remains a powerful heuristic concept but lacks an operational solution.

1.2 Metaphorical Reasoning

Chapter 2 develops the claim that metaphor is central to modelling, not incidental. Drawing on Lakoff and Johnson’s (1980) theory of conceptual metaphor, the authors argue that metaphors serve as “models of knowledge,” structuring how we think, act, and represent phenomena (Ciula et

al., 2023, 43–58). This argument resonates with Cristina Marras’s earlier scholarship on Leibniz, which demonstrated that metaphors were for Leibniz not rhetorical devices but cognitive tools essential to epistemic structuring (Marras 2010; 2008). The book emphasizes the “Factoid” model in prosopography as an example of metaphorical modelling. Factoids, in this context, are not neutral data points but epistemic units shaped by a guiding metaphor of discrete, isolatable “facts” that can be combined into prosopographical knowledge. This metaphor influences the processes of acquisition, storage, and presentation. (Ciula et al. 2023, 56–58). The insight that metaphors guide data modelling is crucial. Metaphors, by mapping a familiar source domain onto an abstract target domain, provide the scaffolding through which data becomes meaningful. However, the analysis does not fully explore how metaphorical reasoning could be systematically applied at the level of schema design or database architecture. As such, the treatment of metaphor remains more illustrative than methodological.

1.3 Semiotics of Modelling

Chapter 3 introduces perhaps the book’s most substantial contribution: a Peircean semiotic framework for understanding modelling as a process of signification (Ciula et al. 2023, 63–91). Drawing on Peirce’s triadic model of the sign—object, representamen, interpretant—the authors conceptualize models as icons: signs that represent their object by virtue of similarity.

Three forms of iconic modelling are distinguished, corresponding to Peirce’s classification of hypoicons:

- **Image-like models**, which resemble their object directly (e.g., a digital reproduction of a manuscript).
- **Relational or diagrammatic models**, which map structural analogies between model and object (e.g., a family tree or network diagram).
- **Metaphor-like models**, which rely on non-standard parallelism to generate new insights (e.g., a social network graph used to represent kinship).

This semiotic perspective allows the authors to articulate both the generative power and the hermeneutic risks of modelling. For example, they warn against the “greediness” of metaphors in network analysis, where the same “link” might ambiguously signify both textual co-reference and social kinship, leading to conflation of semantic planes (Ciula et al. 2023, 82–85). By situating DH modelling within Peircean semiotics, the authors provide a robust theoretical vocabulary for understanding how models signify and how knowledge emerges through representation. This move also connects DH with broader traditions in philosophy of science and semiotics, including Knuuttila (2010) and Kralemann & Lattmann (2013), who emphasize the iconic and mediating functions of models.

1.4 Media Transformation

Chapter 4 expands the framework further by introducing insights from intermedia studies. Models are conceptualized as “media products” constituted by four modalities: material, sensorial, spatiotemporal, and semiotic (Ciula et al. 2023, 95–127). Modelling is thus re-framed as *media transformation*, a process by which one media form is translated into another. A key example is “critical stepwise formalization,” where a medieval drawing is systematically transformed into a digital vector

graphic through a series of sequential operations (Ciula et al. 2023, 121–27). This example highlights how modelling is never merely descriptive but actively transforms the object of study into new media realities, producing both epistemic gains and losses. The analytical reach of this framework is impressive. By bringing materiality and mediality into the discussion, the authors expand DH modelling beyond abstraction into the concrete affordances of media. Yet the framework risks becoming overextended: the categorization of modalities is rich but lacks clarity on how they interact or how scholars might prioritize them in practice.

1.5 Modelling Text: The Anthology

The final chapter departs from conventional argumentation. Instead of a discursive synthesis, it presents a “gallery” of text models: visualizations and diagrams that represent different conceptions of “text” (Ciula et al. 2023, 131–207). These include models of text as a message, as a linguistic expression, as a physical document, and as conceptual work. The anthology-style presentation exemplifies the book’s openness and experimental ethos. It “shows” rather than “tells,” embodying the principle that modelling is itself a mode of argumentation. Yet this strategy has trade-offs. While it effectively illustrates plurality, it does not explicitly integrate the conceptual pillars—pragmatics, metaphor, semiotics, media—into a generative framework. Much of the interpretive synthesis is left to the reader. Moreover, the anthology underscores the book’s tendency to remain descriptive rather than co-creative: it organizes and represents multiple perspectives but does not theorize how such models might themselves become sites of collaborative knowledge production. The absence of sustained engagement with translation and multilingualism is especially felt here. Despite the wheel’s pluralism, it remains monolingual and conceptual, missing the chance to demonstrate translation as a co-equal modelling act. Similarly, the fleeting reference to a middle-out approach earlier in the book is not extended here into a structural principle that could connect these plural models into a more generative, semi-structuralist account of knowledge organization.

2. Critical Analysis

The theoretical ambition of *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice* is to provide Digital Humanities with a renewed conceptual vocabulary for modelling, one that integrates linguistic pragmatics, metaphor theory, semiotics, and intermedia studies. The book succeeds in re-centering modelling as a humanistic, interpretive practice rather than a purely technical process, but its argumentative delivery is uneven. This section examines its strengths and limitations in detail.

2.1 Strengths

One of the book’s most important contributions is its insistence that modelling in DH is not reducible to formalization or algorithmic implementation. By foregrounding **pragmatic modelling**, the authors highlight that modelling is situated in context, intention, and interpretation (Ciula et al. 2023, 19–41). This framing resists a reductive “computational positivism” and aligns DH with traditions of interpretive scholarship. It also echoes McCarty’s (2005) earlier claim that modelling is central to DH precisely because it constitutes a “discipline of making” that blends abstraction and interpretation.

The book's strongest theoretical contribution is its integration of Peircean semiotics into DH modelling. By classifying models as icons (image-like, relational, metaphorical), the authors provide a flexible yet precise vocabulary for describing how models signify (Ciula et al. 2023, 74–85). This approach highlights the epistemic productivity of modelling: how resemblance, analogy, and metaphor can generate knowledge, but also entail interpretive risks. The “greedy metaphor” problem in network analysis—where a “link” may ambiguously signify kinship or textual reference—is a particularly compelling example (Ciula et al. 2023, 82). This semiotic framework situates DH in dialogue with philosophy of science, building on Knuuttila's (2010) call for a non-representational view of models and Kralemann and Lattmann's (2013) semiotic account of models as icons. It strengthens DH's claim to theoretical rigor by grounding its practices in established epistemological traditions. However, the account remains closer to describing epistemic outcomes than to offering generative, co-creative methods.

By treating models as media products, the book extends modelling into material and medial dimensions. The framework of media modalities—material, sensorial, spatiotemporal, semiotic—reminds readers that modelling is not merely abstract but always embodied in form (Ciula et al. 2023, 95–127). This emphasis on pluralism resists hierarchical classifications and underscores the fact that multiple models can coexist, offering different yet valid perspectives on a phenomenon. Chapter 5's anthology of text models exemplifies this pluralism. By presenting multiple conceptions of “text” without privileging one, the authors embody their theoretical claim that modelling is an open-ended, situated practice. This echoes Leibniz's “ocean of knowledge” metaphor, where knowledge is conceived as circulation rather than hierarchical branching (Marras 2008, 209). At the same time, this pluralism is limited in scope, remaining conceptual and monolingual, and leaving unaddressed the equally plural practices of **translation and multilingualism**, which could have been natural extensions of the framework.

2.2 Limitations

While the book is conceptually rich, its structure undermines its effectiveness. The oscillation between systematic theorization (Chapters 1–4) and the anthology-style presentation (Chapter 5) creates a sense of fragmentation. Chapter 5, while visually compelling, does not explicitly demonstrate how the four conceptual pillars interlock, leaving the reader to perform much of the synthesis. This structural choice reflects the book's tendency to “show” rather than “argue,” an approach that has heuristic value but limits its effectiveness as a systematic framework.

Although the authors insist that metaphors are central to modelling, their analysis remains underdeveloped. The example of the Factoid model illustrates how metaphors can guide data practices (pp. 56–58); however, the discussion falls short of demonstrating how metaphorical reasoning could be operationalized in schema design, ontology construction, or database architecture. Given Marras's expertise on Leibniz and metaphor, a deeper engagement at the structural level of data models, beyond project metaphors, would have strengthened the claim that metaphors are not merely rhetorical but cognitive and epistemic tools.

Despite emphasizing pragmatics, the book does not sufficiently address the socio-technical and institutional dimensions of modelling in DH. Questions of infrastructure, power, and epistemic authority—central to critical DH—are largely absent. For instance, how do funding structures, disciplinary boundaries, or software platforms constrain modelling practices? By abstracting modelling

into semiotic and media frameworks, the book risks detaching it from the institutional realities in which DH operates.

The authors aim to provide a “renewed language” for modelling, but the framework is more descriptive than generative. It offers categories (pragmatics, metaphor, semiotics, media) for analysing models but stops short of offering methodological tools for creating new ones. Much of the book frames knowledge in consequentialist terms, emerging as a by-product of modelling, rather than as the result of modelling as a co-creative practice of knowledge production. Translation is discussed primarily as a metaphor for transformation, while its potential role as a co-equal epistemic act remains unexplored. Multilingualism, which could have been a natural extension of the book’s emphasis on interpretive mappings, is almost entirely absent. The lone reference to a middle-out approach (p. 55) remains undeveloped, missing the chance to articulate how semi-structural principles might connect local practices with systemic infrastructures. These gaps limit the book’s generative potential and prevent it from fully addressing the epistemic and infrastructural challenges it identifies.

2.3 Synthesis

In sum, the book’s **strengths** lie in reframing modelling as a humanistic practice, integrating semiotics with unusual depth, and emphasizing pluralism through media and anthology approaches. Its limitations lie in structural unevenness, redundancy, underdeveloped treatment of metaphor, insufficient socio-technical contextualization, and a framework that remains largely descriptive rather than generative. The result is a work that consolidates insights from multiple traditions but does not fully integrate them into a co-creative, multilingual, and infrastructurally generative framework. It is best read as a provocation and resource rather than a definitive theory—an opening that invites further development toward semi-structural and translational approaches to knowledge production.

3. Implications for a Language-Agnostic Knowledge System

Although *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice* is situated primarily within the Digital Humanities, its conceptual proposals resonate far beyond DH. In particular, the book provides essential epistemological tools for the development of a language-agnostic knowledge system, a framework that seeks to represent and organize knowledge independent of any single natural language. By foregrounding iconicity, pragmatic modelling, and metaphorical reasoning, the book offers an implicit foundation for conceiving a system **operationally** rooted in pre-linguistic modes of meaning-making rather than linguistic formalization.

3.1 Iconicity Beyond Language

One of the most substantial contributions is its semiotic framing of models as **icons**, that is, signs that represent by resemblance, analogy, or metaphor (Ciula et al. 2023, 74–85). Unlike symbolic signs, which are tied to linguistic systems, icons signify through structural similarity. This allows models to exist and function outside of specific linguistic codes, which is essential. Suppose knowledge is to be represented in a way that is not limited to English, German, or Persian. In that case, representation must occur at a semiotic level, where resemblance and relational analogy carry meaning. By privileging iconicity over linguistic symbolism, such knowledge can function as a system of conceptual representation that is networked across linguistic divides. This echoes Kralemann and Lattmann’s (2013) argument that models should be understood as icons rather than linguistic

propositions, and it reinforces Marras's (2013) insight that metaphor operates as a structuring principle. A language-agnostic system can thus be conceived as a formalization of these pre-linguistic representational processes. Yet the book itself does not extend this semiotic insight to the organization of multilingual knowledge, leaving open the question of how iconicity might operate across linguistic and cultural divides.

3.2 Pragmatics of Knowledge

The book's concept of pragmatic modelling foregrounds the roles of context, intention, and interpretation in knowledge creation. Meaning does not reside solely in abstract structures but emerges from situated acts of modelling. For a language-agnostic approach, this emphasis on pragmatics is indispensable. Such system cannot be reduced to static ontologies or fixed schemas; it must accommodate context-sensitive variability. Knowledge must be represented in a way that allows for negotiation, reinterpretation, and adaptation to new contexts. This suggests that the system must be built as a semi-structured system where situated acts of use, shape meaning.

While the book does not systematically address translation in the linguistic sense, its semiotic framing offers tools for rethinking it. From a Peircean perspective, translation can be conceived not as a secondary act of linguistic substitution but a primary act of signification: a mediation between *object*, *representamen*, and *interpretant* (Peirce 1934). It can be understood as a metaphor-like modelling process. A translated piece is co-equal with the original, not derivative, because it represents the object through a different but equally valid sign system. This model aligns with the book's insistence that metaphors generate new knowledge by mapping between domains (Ciula et al. 2023, 39–44).

Thus, translation in an agnostic system should be formalized not as a “lossy transfer” but as a *triadic* mediation where *variability* is productive. In that approach, translation “is a process of signification enacting a triadic cooperation between object, representamen (form of a sign) and interpreter (significate outcome of a sign or the thing that is signified) (Ciula et al. 2023, 63)”. Each translation produces interpretive surplus rather than deficit, creating new pathways for knowledge circulation. This is not a conclusion the book itself develops; it is an extension of its semiotic premises in the direction of multilingual and language-agnostic infrastructures.

3.3 Marras, Leibniz, and the Ocean of Knowledge

Cristina Marras's scholarship on Leibniz provides a further point of connection. In contrast to the hierarchical “tree of knowledge,” Leibniz envisioned an “ocean of knowledge”—a metaphor of circulation, interconnection, and availability (Marras 2008, 209). *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities* echoes this in its presentation of the **Text Wheel**, which arranges conceptions of “text” in a circular, non-hierarchical structure (Ciula et al. 2023, 108, 197). For the language-agnostic approach, this metaphor is instructive. A language-agnostic system should not only impose hierarchical taxonomies but also should facilitate dynamic circulation and interconnection. Knowledge should be conceived not as branches from a root. This reconceptualization has direct design implications. Instead of rigid ontological hierarchies, system should employ networked and cyclical structures where concepts are interconnected through iconic, diagrammatic, and metaphorical relations.

3.5 Synthesis

The value of *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities* for development of an alternative system can be distilled into three principles:

1. **Iconicity precedes language** – knowledge structures grounded in resemblance, analogy, and metaphor allow for representation independent of linguistic codes.
2. **Pragmatics precedes formalization** – context, intention, and interpretation shape knowledge before it is encoded into formal schemas.
3. **Metaphor precedes translation** – translation is not derivative but generative, producing variability and new connections.
4. **Structure precedes hierarchy** – knowledge should be organized through semi-structural, middle-out principles that enable circulation and connectivity rather than rigid taxonomies.

Taken together, these principles provide the epistemological substrate for an alternative system. While the book does not explicitly address a language-agnostic approach, its conceptual framework makes clear that modelling can and should be understood as a semiotic and pragmatic process that transcends linguistic boundaries.

4. Case Study: The “Text Wheel” and the Ocean of Knowledge

Among the most striking contributions of *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities* is Chapter 5’s presentation of the “Text Wheel”, a model that arranges different conceptualizations of text in a circular, non-hierarchical structure (Ciula et al. 2023, 140–50). The Text Wheel positions text not as a single definable entity but as a constellation of overlapping perspectives: as message, as linguistic expression, as material document, as cultural work, as knowledge object. This model does not aim for a final definition but rather for a pluralist mapping. Each perspective is situated on the wheel without precedence, highlighting the interconnectedness of diverse scholarly views. Therefore, the Text Wheel functions both descriptively, illustrating the various definitions of text, and prescriptively, as a tool for navigating and mediating disciplinary perspectives.

The circular structure of the Text Wheel contrasts sharply with hierarchical taxonomies that have historically dominated Western thought, particularly the “tree of knowledge.” The tree metaphor, prominent since the Enlightenment, implies a root (foundation), trunk (discipline), and branches (specializations), which organize knowledge into a fixed, stratified system. While effective for structuring domains, the tree is limited in capturing cross-disciplinary circulation, hybridity, and overlapping domains of meaning. The Text Wheel offers an alternative. Refusing hierarchical ordering opens space for multiplicity and acknowledges the coexistence of divergent epistemic frameworks. In this way, the model aligns with the book’s larger agenda: to articulate modelling as a pluralist, interpretive, and pragmatic activity.

The Text Wheel finds a conceptual analogue in Leibniz’s metaphor of the “ocean of knowledge.” As Cristina Marras (Marras 2008, 209) shows, Leibniz deliberately opposed the tree metaphor, which imposed rigid structure, in favor of an ocean, which conveyed circulation, depth, and interconnectedness. For Leibniz, knowledge was not to be systematized into hierarchical categories but understood as a dynamic medium where relations could shift and perspectives overlap. Marras’s interpretation highlights the epistemological radicalism of Leibniz’s metaphor: knowledge is

not a static order but a living process. Similarly, the Text Wheel does not categorize text into essentialist definitions but presents it as a circulating, relational construct. The visual circularity of the model thus performs an epistemic stance: it embodies pluralism rather than merely describing it. For a language-agnostic knowledge system, the Text Wheel offers a concrete demonstration of how non-hierarchical, pluralist modelling can be implemented. The metaphor of the ocean deepens this insight. Just as the ocean enables circulation and interconnection without a fixed hierarchy, a language-agnostic approach should be conceived as a fluid, multi-modal network of representations.

5. Conclusion

Modelling Between Digital and Humanities: Thinking in Practice makes a substantial contribution to the theoretical discourse on Digital Humanities by repositioning modelling as a humanistic practice grounded in pragmatics, metaphor, semiotics, and media transformation. Its most lasting strengths lie in the integration of Peircean semiotics, which provides a rigorous vocabulary for understanding how models signify, and in its pluralist stance, exemplified by the Text Wheel, which resists hierarchical classification in favor of interconnected perspectives. These achievements place the book among the most ambitious theoretical interventions in DH in recent years.

Yet, several limitations are evident. The book remains more descriptive than generative: it catalogues categories for analyzing modelling but rarely provides concrete methodological tools for creating or applying models. This limitation is especially apparent in relation to the **middle-out approach**, which is only fleetingly mentioned in a footnote (p. 55) rather than developed as a guiding principle. A genuinely middle-out, or what might also be called a **semi-structuralist**, approach would be essential for making the book's framework more generative. Such an approach is not only valuable as a pragmatic bridge between current infrastructures and future ones but also as an epistemological principle for how knowledge itself is organized: multi-modal, interconnected, flexible, and open to multiple contexts.

A second limitation concerns the book's treatment of knowledge organization, which lacks equal attention to knowledge production. The authors are careful to emphasize that new knowledge can emerge from modelling and that modelling is not merely reproductive but also interpretive. Their semiotic framework explicitly highlights the epistemic productivity of modelling, and they rightly warn against the risks of "greedy" metaphors that generate unintended connotations (Ciula et al. 2023, 82–85). This is a significant achievement: the book positions modelling as more than mere description, acknowledging that representation can itself be a site of discovery.

However, this remains primarily a **consequentialist view** of knowledge. The new insights that emerge are treated as consequences of modelling practices, outcomes that arise in the mind of the modeller or through the act of representation. What is missing is a systematic account of modelling as a generative and co-creative practice of knowledge production. Modelling could be framed not only as an individual reasoning process but also as a collaborative, pragmatic act of co-authoring knowledge, where interpretive decisions and representational strategies themselves become shared sites of production. A useful counterpoint can be found in an earlier publication by Ciula and Marras (2019), produced within the same research project that later resulted in the book. There, modelling is explicitly framed as a semiotic and generative act, not merely as an interpretive practice with consequential outcomes. In that account, modelling is understood as a primary site of meaning-making, where images, diagrams, and metaphors act as heuristic devices for generating knowledge

(Ciula and Marras 2019, 40–42). This formulation comes closer to recognizing modelling as production rather than consequence, opening the possibility of collaborative, pragmatic co-creation. By comparison, the 2023 volume dilutes this stronger stance: while it acknowledges emergent knowledge, it stops short of articulating modelling as a shared, generative practice. In this respect, the earlier essay offers the sharper theoretical articulation that the book leaves underdeveloped.

The gap is evident in the case of **translation**. In the book, translation appears largely as a metaphor for transformation across media or domains, rather than as a co-equal epistemic act. Yet translation is precisely where the difference between consequentialism and co-creation becomes clear. If treated only metaphorically, translation is a derivative act: it transforms but does not claim equal generative status. If treated instead as a mode of pragmatic modelling, translation becomes a site of **knowledge creation in its own right**—a co-productive act that generates new interpretive pathways while preserving continuity with the original. The book misses this opportunity to extend its own framework from representation and organization into a fuller theory of collaborative and multilingual knowledge production.

Relatedly, the book does not systematically address **multilingualism**. Given its emphasis on models as interpretive mappings and transformations rather than static copies, multilingualism could have been an ideal site for extending the framework. Treating translation not as loss but as productive variability, and framing multilingualism as equal creation of knowledge instead of a Eurocentric focus on accessibility, would have aligned closely with the book's own theoretical ideas. The absence of such an engagement is a notable missed opportunity. It is significant, however, that Ciula and Marras (2019) had already approached translation in a more generative way in their earlier chapter in *Meanings & Co.*. There, translation is not reduced to metaphorical transformation but is presented as a **semiotic operation** that mediates between different representational modes—textual, visual, diagrammatic, and metaphorical (Ciula and Marras 2019, 43–45). This account positions translation as an epistemic act that produces new meaning by shifting across semiotic registers, rather than as a derivative activity reproducing an original. In this respect, the earlier work offered conceptual resources that the 2023 book does not fully develop: a recognition of translation as a **co-equal mode of knowledge production**, aligned with the broader claim that models are not copies but transformative acts of signification.

Taken together, these limitations do not diminish the value of the book but rather indicate the directions in which its framework could be extended. A fuller account of middle-out semi-structuralism, encompassing knowledge production and organization, as well as translation and multilingualism as central modelling practices, would deepen its generative capacity. These are also precisely the areas where a future language-agnostic knowledge system could build upon the book's foundations, extending its interpretive humanism into infrastructural and multilingual terrains. In this sense, *Modelling Between Digital and Humanities* is best understood not as a closed system but as an opening (or a point of departure): a descriptive vocabulary that invites others to take the next step toward generative, semi-structured, and multilingual infrastructures of knowledge.

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